

D6.1 – Stakeholder Engagement, Dissemination and Communication Plan

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Executive summary

This strategy aims to steer, harmonise and set out URBANE's stakeholder engagement, communication, dissemination and exploitation (SE/C/D/E) activities throughout the project's lifetime. Progress in achieving its objectives will be laid out, monitored and evaluated in the project's periodic reporting activities in M18 and M30. The key objectives of this plan are to:

- Identify communication, dissemination and exploitation goals, key messages and target groups;
- Define the stakeholder engagement and network opportunities and activities;
- Lay out the project's identity, channels and tools;
- Identify events, journals, academic papers and further opportunities;
- Establish the planning, monitoring and evaluation mechanisms.

This plan is not set in stone: it is a living document that should be adapted throughout the project's progress and development according to needs.

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Glossary of Terms and Acronyms

ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
AB	Advisory Board
ABMs	Agent-Based Models
ADVs	Automated Delivery Vehicles
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CCAM	Connected Cooperative Automated Mobility
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FAIR (principle)	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reused
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LLs	Living Labs
NDA	Nearby Delivery Area
PI	Physical Internet
RFID	Radio Frequency Identification
SE/C/D/E	Stakeholder engagement, communication, dissemination and exploitation
TRL	Technology readiness level
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

1.1. What is URBANE?

URBANE is a 3.5-year Horizon Europe (2022-2026) project that focuses on novel, sustainable, safe, resilient and effective **last-mile delivery solutions** combining green automated vehicles and shared space utilisation models. The project will put in place **four Lighthouse Living Labs (LLs)** – Helsinki (FI), Bologna (IT), Valladolid (ES) and Thessaloniki (EL) - that will demonstrate TRL7/8 efficient, replicable and socially acceptable innovative last-mile delivery solutions (Wave 1 solutions), building on existing assets.

Lessons learned will be facilitated by an **Innovation Transferability Platform** comprising Digital Twinning Tools, open models, smart contracts governed by blockchain technology, and a data-driven Impact Assessment Radar. These will enable the adaptation and replication of Wave 1 solutions in **two Twinning LLs** in Barcelona (ES) and Karlsruhe (DE).

URBANE's commitment to upscaling is further strengthened by the engagement of **six early adopters** or follower cities, namely Aarhus (DK), La Rochelle (FR), Mechelen (BE), Prague (CZ), Ravenna (IT) and Antwerp (BE). They will produce feasibility studies on the adoption of innovations, thus stimulating the creation of additional LLs across Europe.

The project's consortium comprises **39 partners** and an external partner from **12 different EU Member states**, led by INLECOM, a leading digital innovation provider, responsible for the twinning infrastructure and open models' library of the project

1.2. What are the goals of this plan?

The primary goal of the plan is to **strategically, openly, and comprehensively promote the impact and outcomes of the project**, as well as **engage a diversity of relevant stakeholders** throughout its lifecycle. The objectives can be broken down into four categories.

TABLE 1 - GOALS OF URBANE'S SE/C/D/E PLAN

Cluster	Goals
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Goals and overall strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lay out a harmonised and clear project identity used and implemented by all consortium members • Outline the project's key messages, channels and tools to guarantee the visibility of the project. • Establish quantitative and qualitative SE/C/D/E objectives, notably through a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)
Stakeholder engagement and cooperation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify primary and secondary target groups, entry points for cooperation and feedback loops with user needs • Raise awareness in the last-mile logistics sector of the project
Dissemination and Exploitation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish a clear library of events, academic journals and other opportunities to disseminate and exploit project findings, best practices and results • Create synergies and interest with active external organisations and networks, other EU projects as well as national initiatives and networks in the use case countries. • Support the exploitation of results: research, commercial, and other stakeholders

1.3. Key Messages

The following key messages are **ready-to-use tailored statements** which cover project-wide objectives. Each SE/C/D/E activity should be in line with the following messages to ensure consistency:

1. URBANE will enable the development of novel, sustainable, safe, resilient and effective last-mile delivery solutions combining green automated vehicles and shared space utilisation models.
2. URBANE is testing solutions in four Lighthouse Living Labs (Helsinki, Bologna, Valladolid and Thessaloniki), which will be later replicated and adapted in two twinning Living Labs (Barcelona and Karlsruhe) and further upscaled in six early adopter cities.
3. URBANE puts a strong emphasis on the dissemination and exploitation of results through an Innovation Transferability Platform comprising Digital Twinning Tools, open models, smart contracts governed by blockchain technology, and a data-driven Impact Assessment Radar.
4. There has never been a greater demand for last-mile deliveries. The World Economic Forum predicts a rise of 78% in last-mile deliveries by 2030 in urban areas, leading to higher congestion and pollution levels, and immense logistics issues. URBANE is tackling this challenge head-on.
5. URBANE's vision addresses business, technical and regulatory challenges of green last-mile logistics while fulfilling the project's innovation and commercial ambitions.

1.5 URBANE Outputs Mapping to GA Commitments

TABLE 2: DELIVERABLE ADHERENCE TO GRANT AGREEMENT DELIVERABLE AND WORK DESCRIPTION.

URBANE GA ITEM	URBANE GA ITEM DESCRIPTION	DOCUMENT CHAPTER(S)	JUSTIFICATION
DELIVERABLE			

<p>D6.1</p>	<p>Report monitoring engagement mechanisms and planned activities.</p> <p>A detailed 'plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities' will be provided on M6 and will be periodically updated in alignment with the project's progress.</p> <p>The progress of the activities will be reported as integral parts of the periodic reports on M18 and M30. The final Dissemination and Communications Activities report will include the summary of all related activities.</p>	<p>ALL</p>	<p>This deliverable goes over all the communication, dissemination, exploitation and stakeholder engagement activities, strategies and target groups.</p>
<p>TASK</p>			
<p>Task 6.1 Stakeholder Engagement, Dissemination and Communications (M1-M42) Sub-tasks: 6.1.1</p>	<p>ST6.1.1 Dissemination and Communication strategy (POLIS).</p> <p>An initial dissemination and communication plan is developed at the start of the project jointly with all the partners. The plan defines the appropriate channels and tools for outreach towards the outside world, synergies with other projects and initiatives, as well as lists relevant external events to further enhance the project's dissemination and take-up activities.</p> <p>The initial draft of this plan is included in section 2.2. A project logo, branding guidance and an overall corporate identity (report template, PowerPoint template, leaflet, etc.) is developed to give the project a common and</p>	<p>ALL</p>	<p>This deliverable was conceptualised by POLIS, with the input of consortium partners to define the channels, tools, synergies, target groups, publications, events and a range of other activities essential for the project's stakeholder engagement, communication, dissemination and exploitation.</p>

	<p>recognisable identity. This identity will be used on all project and local dissemination materials. Communications will rely on electronic tools such as the website, social media (Twitter, Youtube, LinkedIn etc.), and direct mailings. However, these will be accompanied by innovative communication methods, such as for example online streaming series, Open Innovation Days in each local LL site, etc. Besides from creating its own ecosystem of stakeholders from the mentioned URBANE urban logistics value chain target groups, the dissemination and communication activities will capitalise on the POLIS, EITUM and ALICE networks' channels and large audience on social media by creating ad-hoc campaigns centred on key communications milestones (e.g. project outputs, factsheets, publications, conferences, articles). Moreover, they will further capitalise on the POLIS and EIT UM Working Group activities, as opportunities for showcasing the innovations to the networks' respective members.</p>		
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1.6. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

TABLE 2 - OVERVIEW OF DELIVERABLE CONTENT

Section	Content	Relevance to other tasks or deliverables
Introduction	Overview of the project's description, the goals of the plan, and key messages.	Useful for all WPs to communicate on the project (surveys, interviews, presentations, etc).
Stakeholder engagement and community building	Breakdown of the target groups, networks and initiatives linked to last-mile logistics, capacity building actions, and the elaboration of the advisory board and city platform.	ALL, particularly WP2, WP 4, WP5 WP6: <i>particularly ST6.1.2 City Platform, ST6.1.3 Capacity Building, Task 6.2 Liaison with other initiatives</i>
Project Identity	Guidelines on URBANE's visual identity (logo, colours, fonts, etc.) and correct mention of EU and Civitas funding disclaimers. Overview of the project descriptions	All WPs
Tools	Overview of URBANE's physical and online channels, tools and material. Library of potential events and publications URBANE can participate in.	All WPs
Exploitation	Overview of the exploitation of the project results.	WP3, WP4 and WP5 WP2: <i>particularly Task 6.3 Adoption Feasibility Studies by Follower Cities (M19-M40), Task 6.4 Policy</i>

		<i>Package and Adoption Roadmap (M19-M42)</i>
Planning and Monitory	Recap of the activity and dissemination registers and procedures, use of data, open science and intellectual property rights.	<i>ALL WPs, particularly WP7</i>

2. Stakeholder Engagement and Community Building

2.1. Target Groups

The URBANE target groups are based on the urban logistics value chain. Each target group should be approached in a tailored way, for specific objectives, activities and outputs, to ensure strong bottom-up and top-down engagements.

Urban planners, public authorities and regulators

This group includes local, metropolitan, regional and national stakeholders in the LL, follower cities, members of the City Platform as well as EU regulators and strategic planners. URBANE will focus on urban planning and local regulations linked to freight and logistics, as well as the implementation of Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans and/or Sustainable Urban Logistics Plans. This target group will benefit from the project's **policy deliverables and adoption roadmap** which could multiply upscaling of the project's solutions.

Courier & Transport Operators, Shippers (business) Fleet Owners, Urban distribution hub/centre Operators

These target groups includes:

- Couriers, urban transport operators and third-party logistics companies.
- Shippers, which are responsible for organising and transporting goods from one point to another. In the context of urban logistics, shippers can include local businesses, e.g. shop owners as well as public entities.
- Fleet owners, which are companies that own fleets of urban logistics vehicles (companies that transport goods or companies that supply their vehicles to transport companies).
- Urban distribution hubs or centres, which facilitate the shipment of goods to urban areas by consolidating deliveries and improving efficiency in the distribution process.

They will be mobilised to **(re)view project results, provide feedback on the tools and solutions,** and will have the opportunity to **adopt and commercialise** URBANE solutions. They may be interested in the research and frameworks developed by the project, particularly the innovations tested in the use cases (LL, Twinning LLs and follower cities), the replication of innovation delivery methods, business models and impact assessments developed in the project, and more.

Academia and research institutes

External academic and research findings, projects and initiatives will be a key factor in the success of the project which will build on existing protocols and knowledge. However, the project's researchers will also contribute to research on green last-mile logistics through open-source publications, synergies with other researchers and by presenting results at conferences and other events. Researchers will have the opportunity **to use and tap into URBANE's findings,** as well as **give their feedback** and **review results.** The objectives are to upscale and diffuse the project's results within the academic community and beyond.

Sector associations, end-users and society

This target group will **directly benefit** from the last-mile urban logistics solutions tested in the living labs, which will further be upscaled, thanks to their environmental, economic, social and user-centric benefits. In addition, this target group will have the opportunity to **actively participate and engage** in all demonstrations through **user acceptance tests, co-design workshops, feedback loops and the analysis of their acceptability levels** of innovative technologies. It is essential to get end-users and civil society on board to ensure the adoption and acceptance of the innovations. The project will **show the benefits of the innovative solutions** and **raise awareness of the sustainability needs of freight and logistics.**

Within this group, there are sectorial associations and networks that bring together companies and other stakeholders in the urban logistics sector to promote and develop business. URBANE's results can **enrich their activities with their members,** as well as include their members **in reviewing project results and providing feedback** while **exploring opportunities to support upscaling** and **take-up** of the solutions.

Other Stakeholders that will be involved include:

- **Infrastructure Service Providers** are private or public companies that manage the transport infrastructure, providing services like maintenance.
- **ICT service providers** are companies that provide digital connectivity and interfaces (GPS, tracking, links to warehouses, transport providers, etc.). They can provide updated insights into the latest solutions in last-mile green logistics, particularly

linked to the collection and storage of mobility data, data solutions, blockchain infrastructure, etc.

- **Technology providers** can inform URBANE of new innovative solutions that can be tested by the project, as well as uptake innovative solutions from the project.
- **Liability Companies** are companies that provide insurance and legal services related to the urban logistics sector.

2.2. Networks and Engagement

URBANE will cooperate with external initiatives, projects and strategic alliances in the green last-mile logistics sector. The goals are to ensure **knowledge transfer**, build **momentum with and from other initiatives** or clusters of projects, and **establish synergies**, particularly through participation in conferences, workshops and other events. Collaborations, clustering and liaising with other initiatives will be guided by topic-oriented activities (e.g. joining events), the need to facilitate dialogues between experts in the field and public authorities, and the aim of increasing URBANE's public visibility.

A list of relevant organisations includes:

- **Networks**, which will disseminate the project to their members: [ALICE](#), [POLIS](#) and [EITUM](#), as well as [C40](#), [Climate KIC](#) and [OPEN ENLoCC](#), [European Social Simulation Association](#), [European Complex Systems Society](#), [NECTAR cluster 3](#). Activities may include sharing URBANE's findings, tools and publications with members, inviting them to attend URBANE's events and final conference, and creating synergies through co-organised webinars or news articles.
- **EU-funded projects**: [DECARBOMILE](#) (URBANE's sister project), the urban logistics cluster of projects ([LEAD](#), [SENATOR](#) and [ULaaDs](#)), other projects like GREEN LOG, [PLANET](#), [BOOSTLOG](#), [MOVE21](#), GeoSense, [SPINE](#), the EIT UM funded projects such as FlexCurb, [LogiSmile](#), Coding the Curbs and Tactic and other strategic projects, such as PrepDSpace4Mobility, an EU funded project that contributes to the development of a common European mobility data space. Activities may include the joint organisation of webinars and workshops as well as the co-creation of sessions at European and international events (e.g. TRA, TRB, ITS World and European Congress, Tomorrow.Mobility World Congress, ALICE events, POLIS Conference, International Urban Freight Conference, International Physical Internet Conference, the Civitas Conference, the Urban Mobility Days, World Society for Transport and Land Use research symposium, EURO Working Group on Transportation etc.).

- **The CIVITAS initiative.** Activities may include sharing results on the website, playing an active role in contributing to the initiative, particularly [CIVITAS ELEVATE](#), exchanging findings and results with the other urban logistics projects of CIVITAS, and integrating the CIVITAS corporate design framework in URBANE's.
- **Cooperation with international initiatives:** [SLoCaT](#), [ITE](#), Eltis, C40, UN bodies, CCAM partnership, 2Zero partnership, etc.
- **Local partners, initiatives and projects** linked to the LLs
- Cooperation with and support of LLs in **100 Climate Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030** Valladolid, Helsinki, Bologna, Thessaloniki and Barcelona. [NetZeroCities](#) provides support to cities that are part of the EU Mission through expertise and services.

2.3. Capacity Building

URBANE's capacity-building activities will be centred on **interactive knowledge sharing** through the demonstration of the results of the project and discussions on hot topics. URBANE will define which capacity-building activities will be undertaken within the consortium and with external partners including those from the CIVITAS initiative. The project will organise regular **webinars and workshops**, as well as an **Open Innovation Day** in each LL, activities on the **City Platform** and the project's **final conference**. The latter will occur at the end of the project to disseminate the project's findings and identify exploitation and upscaling opportunities for the solutions.

FIGURE 1 - MIND MAP OF CAPACITY BUILDING ACTIVITIES

The mind map of URBANE's capacity-building activities presents the general framework that will be followed by the project. However, additional activities will be created on an ad hoc and on-needs basis principle in a dynamic, flexible and modular way.

2.4. Advisory Board

URBANE's Advisory Board (AB) will be a **small group of experts** that will **guide the project consortium on defined activities**, notably on adoption and take-up actions, and the promotion of knowledge transfer and exploitation of the project's best practices. They will represent a well-balanced group covering multiple facets of the green last-mile logistics sector, from research and commercial interests to cities and associations.

In addition, the AB will have the opportunity to **participate in technical and strategic meetings** to discuss standardisation questions, the validation of key results from the LLs, and any key challenge encountered through the project. They will provide recommendations to the City Platform to help with the user experiences, content and exploitation.

2.5. City Platform

The City Platform will involve **external cities and regions** that will provide guidance to the consortium, validate the project's results and support the upscaling of its solutions. The group will be composed of public authorities that will mainly support the **"Policy Package and Adoption Roadmap"** task which includes, but is not limited to, the:

- participation in policy dialogues on urban freight planning and innovation with EU institutions;
- contribution to the standardisation of safety, security and cybersecurity measures and identification of results from the project that can be standardised (e.g. smart contracts or models);
- elaboration of policy recommendations based on the outcomes and lessons from the living labs and the project.

In addition, the City Platform members will contribute to the **identification of local authorities' requirements and expectations in last-mile deliveries and URBANE solutions**. This will be done both through interviews and surveys, bilateral meetings with consortium members, and feedback meetings on various pillars of the project (the tools, business and operational models, demonstrations, and more).

Finally, they will have the opportunity to participate in capacity building, online webinars and training sessions, as detailed in section 4.3., and can partake in bilateral meetings with consortium partners developing the URBANE tools.

3. Project Identity

3.1. Visual Identity: Name, Logo, Colours and Fonts

URBANE's **full project name** is "Upscaling Innovative Green Urban Logistics Solutions Through Multi-Actor Collaboration and Physical Internet (PI) - Inspired Last Mile Deliveries". The acronym should always be in capital letters.

The **logo** is available in colour, white (to be used for certain coloured backgrounds) and grayscale in JPEG, PNG, EPS and AI formats. The logo must appear fully intact no matter its size – it should never be stretched, altered or distorted.

FIGURE 2 - URBANE LOGO IN COLOUR

FIGURE 3 - URBANE LOGO IN BLACK AND WHITE

URBANE has three primary colours, which are visible in the logo, and nine secondary colours showcased below.

FIGURE 4 - URBANE COLOUR PALETTE

Finally, the project’s font for Word and PowerPoint is Calibri, and for digital communication, it is Proxima Nova.

3.2. Descriptions

To facilitate the communication of URBANE, the following sentences can be used by all partners to present the project concisely, from a sentence to two paragraphs.

TABLE 3 - PROJECT DESCRIPTIONS

One-liner	
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	<p>URBANE is a Horizon Europe (2022-2026) project on novel, sustainable, safe, resilient and effective last-mile delivery solutions, combining green automated vehicles and shared space utilisation models</p>
Two-liner/One paragraph	<p>URBANE is a 3.5-year Horizon Europe (2022-2026) project on novel, sustainable, safe, resilient and effective last-mile delivery solutions, combining green automated vehicles and shared space utilisation models. The project will test innovative solutions in four Lighthouse Living Labs (Helsinki, Bologna, Valladolid and Thessaloniki) as well as two Twinning Living Labs (Barcelona and Karlsruhe) and six early adopter follower cities.</p>
Two paragraphs	<p>URBANE is a 3.5-year Horizon Europe (2022-2026) project on novel, sustainable, safe, resilient and effective last-mile delivery solutions, combining green automated vehicles and shared space utilisation models. The project will test innovative TRL7/8 efficient, replicable and socially acceptable innovative last-mile delivery solutions (Wave 1 solutions) solutions in four Lighthouse Living Labs (Helsinki, Bologna, Valladolid and Thessaloniki).</p> <p>The project is dedicated to upscaling, adapting and replicating its solutions through its two Twinning Living Labs (Barcelona and Karlsruhe) which will implement the Wave 1 solutions, and its six early adopter follower cities. The project's consortium comprises 39 partners and an external partner from 12 different EU Member states, led by INLECOM, a leading digital innovation provider, responsible for the twinning infrastructure and open models' library of the project.</p>

3.3. EU Funding disclaimers

A systematic acknowledgement of EU support must be made in all URBANE SE/C/D/E activities. This includes social media posts, factsheets, presentations, posters, brochures, media relations, and other materials. To correctly follow the regulations, a tailored checklist was elaborated.

Your material includes:

- ✓ A clearly visible **EU funding emblem** ([download here](#)) with the following **statement** “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101069782.”
 - The EU emblem must have **appropriate prominence** when displayed with other logos (at least the same size as the biggest logo).
 - For the statement acknowledging EU funding, use the following **fonts**: Arial, Auto, Calibri, Garamond, Tahoma, Trebuchet, Ubuntu or Verdana.
 - **Do not use underlined text, italic or font effects** in the funding statement. Use a **black, white or blue (EU flag colour) font** depending on the background.
 - The funding statement **can be translated** into a local language, where appropriate.
 - The statement “Funded by the European Union” or “Co-funded by the European Union” must always be spelt out in full and placed next to the emblem.
 - Any publication or material prepared by the consortium members, even if at the national level, shall **at least display the project logo, EU flag and funding statement**. This includes material done on behalf of URBANE and/or in the framework of the tasks assigned in the project to the partners.
 - For further information, please consult [The use of the EU Emblem in the Context of EU programmes 2021- 2027](#)

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- ✓ Always include the CIVITAS logo next to the EU logo.

- ✓ If applicable, include the following **statement**: “URBANE is funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement

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4. Tools

4.1. Physical: Project leaflet and banner

By early 2023, URBANE will have a project leaflet and banner – key products for external events. The project leaflet and banner will be used to explain the project and its core elements. The flyer will be, both in digital version (with hyperlinks) and print version. The printable version may contain QR codes to allow users to access the linked content).

The number of flyers distributed during conferences and sent via email depends on the contacts and events which will be organised during the course of the project. Contents and prints will be provided by the Consortium.

4.2. Online: Website, newsletters, press releases, videos and social media

A dedicated URBANE **website** will be available in early 2023 (see Annex – Figure 5).

At least twice a year, the URBANE **newsletter** will be distributed to its subscribers to update them on the progress of the project and the Living Labs, significant results, and opportunities to get involved.

POLIS will be responsible for promoting the newsletter and will develop its content with unique articles (interviews, photos, event recaps, etc.), collect inputs from the consortium, and send it to the subscribers in line with data protection and GDPR (subscribers’ data will be collected only for the newsletter and during the duration of the project) requirements, as well as in line with the project identity and brand. Each partner will be also asked to forward it to their mailing lists/contacts.

A [press release](#) was posted online and disseminated via the project's social media channels at the outset of the project.

In addition, URBANE will create several **videos** to illustrate its ambitions and living labs.

Finally, **social media** is one of the most important tools for a project's stakeholder engagement as well as for its communication, dissemination and exploitation activities. It is an efficient way to reach a large and targeted external audience. URBANE is on three platforms:

- [Twitter page](#), for rapid and on-the-spot updates in a more relaxed tone. This channel is a key tool during in-person events, allowing us to tag consortium members and pertinent external stakeholders.
- [LinkedIn page](#), for longer and more formal posts on more detailed results, opportunities and findings.
- [YouTube channel](#), to share videos, webinars and other recorded events.

The main objectives of using social media are:

1. To share project information, activities and results
2. To increase the involvement in the project's activities and events and allow for interaction
3. To widen the outreach of the project's outcomes
4. To allow for an interactive dissemination
5. To analyse the audience statistics and feedback to adjust the communication strategy.

4.3. Publications and Events

URBANE will participate regularly in a **range of local, national and European events** through sessions, pitches, academic posters, papers, stands and more. The main goal is to ensure the dissemination of the project's activities and results, network with other initiatives, learn from others, share ideas, and offer opportunities for the exploitation of findings.

TABLE 4 - POTENTIAL PARTICIPATION IN EVENTS

Geographic Scale	Event
Local and National	Use Case specific events include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • E-TECH EUROPE 2023 – Bologna – 19/20th April 2023 (https://e-tech.show/): Exhibition and Conference on Advanced Batteries and Innovative Technologies for Electric Vehicle Production;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ECOMONDO 2023 – Rimini – 7-10th November 2023 (https://en.ecomondo.com/): Green Technology Expo; • Italian National Conference on SUMP (Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans) 2023; • European Mobility Week 2023 – Ravenna; • European Mobility Week 2023 – Bologna; • Kick-off Meeting Bologna 18-19 May 2023 – GRETA (Greening Regional fReight Transport in fuAs) Interreg Central Europe Project • XV Congreso de Ingeniería de Transporte - CIT 2025 • Annual conference for the presentation of the research results of the Contract Logistics Observatory "Gino Marchet" 2023 • Netcomm Forum 17 18 May 2023 Allianz MiCo, Milan: The digital commerce & retail event • Salón del Automóvil Híbrido y Eléctrico - SAHE (Hybrid and Electric Motor Show) - April 2023 • Congreso Español ITS
European	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ALICE, POLIS and EITUM internal and external events • Transport Research Arena (TRA) 2024 (15-18/04/2024) – Dublin, Ireland • Tomorrow.Mobility World Congress (EIT Urban Mobility) • Civitas Forum Conference • Interdisciplinary Conference of Production, Logistics and traffic • Urban Mobility Days • TEN-T Days • ITS European Congress • POLIS Annual Conference • Urban Future Conference • International Transport Summit (ITF) Summit • Transportation Research Board Annual Meeting • PARCEL+POST EXPO October 24, 25, 26, 2023 RAI Amsterdam, the Netherlands • Transport Logistic – Munich 9th – 12th May 2023

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EPOSS Annual Forum
International	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ITS World Congress • Transforming Transportation (World Bank) • World Conference on Transport Research Society • Transportation Research Board (TRB) Annual Meeting • International Physical Internet Conference (IPIC) • Odysseus (International Workshop on Transport and Logistics)

In addition, URBANE will also organise events, including webinars, workshops, and seminars to increase the visibility of the project. These include **workshops with Lighthouse LL stakeholders**, **technical workshops** with other metropolitan public authorities, **online streaming series**, a **final conference** at the end of the project and more.

The project's flagship events are the "**Open Innovation Days**" which will take place at the end of the demonstration period in each LL city to showcase the solutions developed and partners involved, as well as create interest among local and European stakeholders and disseminate the results of the work achieved within URBANE.

In regards to **publications**, URBANE will target both magazines and scientific journals, as described in the table below.

TABLE 5 - POTENTIAL PARTICIPATION IN MAGAZINES AND ACADEMIC JOURNALS

Nature	Name
Magazine	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cities in Motion: Cities in motion - POLIS Network • Cities Today: Home - Cities Today (cities-today.com) • Intelligent Transport: Intelligent Transport • Revolve Magazine: Quarterly insights into a changing world. REVOLVE Magazine • Urban Transport Magazine: Urban Transport Magazine - (urban-transport-magazine.com)

<p>Academic Journals (Open access only)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open Research Europe Publishing Platform: Open Research Europe Open Access ... Open Research Europe (europa.eu) • European Transport Research Review Home (springeropen.com) • Transportation Research Interdisciplinary Perspectives Journal ScienceDirect.com by Elsevier • International Journal of Transportation Science and Technology ScienceDirect.com by Elsevier • IET Digital Library: IET Intelligent Transport Systems (theiet.org) • European Journal of Transport and Infrastructure Research (tudelft.nl) • Transportation Engineering Journal ScienceDirect.com by Elsevier • Future Transportation An Open Access Journal from MDPI • Transportation Home (springer.com) • Journal of Urban Mobility • Journal of Artificial Societies and Social Simulation • PLOS ONE • Collective Intelligence
<p>Newsletters</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • POLIS Internal and External Newsletters • ALICE Newsletter • EIT Urban Mobility Newsletter • Civitas • Urban Mobility Weekly – Autonomy • LSE Cities Newsletter • EU Urban Mobility Observatory Newsletter (Eltis) • SIMSOC

5. Exploitation

The exploitation of the project results will be in line with the strategy proposed by EITUM in its role as Exploitation Manager and closely linked to WP5 (Business Plans and Commercialisation). The latter aims to advance URBANE's solutions commercially through market and business exploitation strategies through a tailored approach called "Exploitation Factory". It follows a five-step approach including (i) evaluating the Market Readiness Level, (ii) evaluating the quality of results, (iii) identifying Partnerships for IP exploitation, (iv) developing a Commercialisation Roadmap, (v) engaging in IPR management, and (vi) identifying Funding opportunities along with a post-project 5-year exploitation plan and results reporting.

In a nutshell, URBANE's exploitation strategy will focus on **activities linked to market upscaling and the uptake of innovations developed or tested in the project** through clear business plans and commercialisation strategies. A strong emphasis will be put on Intellectual Property Rights Management, transparency and the FAIR principles.

The project activities directly linked to exploitation include:

- ✓ Participation of the **Advisory Board** in the adoption and take-up of URBANE's solutions by sharing their experience, input and feedback
- ✓ **Collaborative Innovation Days** in the LLs or the final conference will both enable the communication and dissemination of project results as well as create opportunities for the exploitation of URBANE's solutions. Such events will also be co-organised with other European projects, initiatives and networks.
- ✓ Urbane's **Innovation Transferability Platform** will enable the transfer, adaptation and replication of Wave 1 solutions to the two Twinning LLs. Development of IT Tools: Digital Twinning Tools, open models, smart contracts governed by blockchain infrastructure and a data-driven Impact Assessment Radar. These will support the assessment of the impacts of the solutions and driven decision-making particularly the Impact Assessment Radar.
- ✓ Replication through **Twinning LLs**: Barcelona and Karlsruhe
- ✓ Adoption by **Six Follower Cities** with the potential to create new LL (adoption feasibility studies) and the Follower Cities Forum
- ✓ Using the EIT Urban Mobility Marketplace to:
i) showcase the market-ready innovative solutions developed in URBANE and

connect them with potential customers. Links will be created with other Marketplaces to increase the digital visibility of the solutions developed (e.g. Smart Cities Marketplace, ALICE Marketplace, etc.)

ii) support the Market Observatory for Physical Internet in Urban Logistics, a hub that will gather high-quality data and information identified/developed during the project to achieve a better understanding of last mile flagship delivery market, regulations, and trends. The hub will also consider digital transformation and consumer behaviour towards Physical Internet and will accelerate the decarbonisation process of urban logistics by 2030.

- ✓ **Collaborations** with European projects, initiatives and networks

TABLE 6 - EXPLOITATION TOOLS AND CHANNELS

Tool	Aims
<u>Horizon Results Platform</u>	<p>A Platform to showcase project results, create synergies, gather interest from private and public sectors, network with partners, showcase findings to policymakers, and more.</p> <p>Potential Actions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publish URBANE’s results • Learn more about exploitation strategies and tools through their webinars and events.
<u>Horizon Results Booster</u>	<p>An EC initiative which maximises the impact of publicly funded research within the EU</p> <p>Potential Actions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Free mentoring on boosting dissemination and exploitation of results of EU projects (e.g. portfolio and dissemination strategies, business plan development, “go to market” services). • Services available between 2020-2024
<u>Enterprise Europe Network</u>	<p>A network that helps small and medium-sized enterprises innovate and grow internationally.</p> <p>Potential Actions:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SMEs in the consortium could benefit from their services: advice and support, as well as partnering and business opportunities
European IP helpdesk	<p>A free-of-charge service that supports SMEs and beneficiaries of EU-funded research projects in managing their Intellectual Property.</p> <p>Potential Actions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> They offer a broad range of informative material, a helpline service, online and on-site training, publications, and local IP ambassadors throughout Europe. But no legal advice. They offer both awareness-building activities and support in successful exploitation.
European Business Angel Network	<p>A European network representing the early-stage investor community gathering over 100 member organisations in more than 50 countries today. (Start Ups)</p> <p>Actions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pitching in competitions (in cooperation with Horizon Booster) Annual events in partnership with EU agencies
EIT Urban Mobility Marketplace	<p>A platform that showcases leading market-ready urban mobility innovative solutions, knowledge, and opportunities.</p> <p>Actions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support the Market Observatory for Physical Internet in Urban Logistics Increase the visibility of URBANE's solutions and connect them with potential customers

For a more detailed overview of the exploitation of the project results, please see the table in the Annex "Exploitation of the project's major results".

6. Planning and Monitoring

6.1. Activity Registers and Dissemination Procedures

To monitor the impacts of the communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities carried out by the URBANE consortium, a tracker was established. This tool must be updated frequently by all partners to monitor whether the existing approach is effective. POLIS in turn will collect all these inputs and will compile every six months a summary report of all the activities performed.

6.2. Data Usage and Access to Information

In URBANE, data will be used, processed and stored in line with the GDPR and any other applicable national, international, and EU regulations on data protection. Data must be utilised for a clear, safe, confidential, and lawful purpose in a transparent, equitable, and legal manner. Compliance with the following regulations will be ensured throughout the project by all partners:

- Regulation (EU) 2018/1725 of the European Parliament and the Council concerning the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by institutions, bodies, offices, and agencies of the Union and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Regulation (EC) No. 45/2001 and Decision No. 1247/2002/EC (OJ L 295, 21.11.2018, p. 39).
- The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity provides the research community in Europe with a framework for self-regulation across all academic fields and research contexts.
- GDPR, or Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of April 27, 2016, on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (OJ L 119, 4.5.2016, p. 1).
- The Universal Declaration of Human Rights and the Convention 108 for the Protection of Individuals with Regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data.
- National laws appropriate to each partner country for specific activities including living labs.

Data governance, management and protection, as well as ethical requirements, are ensured in all data-intensive tasks and monitored through URBANE's Data Management and Ethics plan (D7.1). This will ensure that research is conducted at the highest level of integrity, quality and transparency – particularly for topics in grey zones like AI software use and development and personal data. The plan will cover the full life cycle of data collection, processing and use in URBANE including:

- details on how to handle research data both during and after the project is completed.
- which data will be gathered, processed, or published
- the standards and methods used
- how data will be selected and stored, whether they will be shared or made available through open access (including after the end of the project).

6.3. Open Science and Intellectual Property Rights

In the area of last-mile logistics, URBANE will help the EU achieve its policies, research objectives, and regulations. Therefore, the project is built on principles of **open science practices**, particularly when it comes to the publication and use of URBANE's results, public datasets, and conclusions. However, it is necessary to underline the importance of confidentiality when undertaking public dissemination: in line with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the confidentiality of business partners' competitive information, the access to some information and results remain open only internally.

All of URBANE's publicly accessible publications will be stored in repositories available in **Open AIRE** (Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe) which links over 450 million research metadata records. These publications will be added either through self-archiving publishing (open access for a maximum of 6 months) or open access publishing (open-access journals).

The goal is to maximise the exploitation, reuse and reproducibility of the project's results and foster an environment of collaboration and interdisciplinary research. URBANE will therefore ensure that its findings, data assets, scientific publications, protocols and other relevant outputs, particularly linked to the Living Labs, are in line with the goals of the **European Open Science Cloud**, which offers a federated environment where scientific data, tools and services can be used, and the **FAIR principles** for data and services (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reused). All the public deliverables will be published on the URBANE website – which will stay active for two years after the end of the project.

To give an example, the **Forum for Follower Cities** and **Advisory Board** are key project initiatives to promote the upscaling and replication of the results of the Living Labs and the project.

6.4. Key Performance Indicators

The following key performance indicators (KPIs) will be used to guide the SE/C/D/E project activities. They will support the consortium in tracking and assessing the project's outreach in regard to social media, press coverage, publications, and events. To register and monitor these activities, a tracker was built and made available to all parties.

TABLE 7 - URBANE'S KPIS

	Indicator	Performance Midterm	Performance end of project
Leaflets	Distributed	50	150
Website	Visits	150/month	250/month
Newsletter	Subscribers	50	100
Newsletter Number	Sent Newsletters	3	7
LinkedIn	Followers	100	250
Twitter	Followers	50	150
YouTube	Views	20	80
Final event	Attendees	N/A	+ 65
Media Coverage	Coverage	3 minimum	6 minimum
Scientific articles	Published/Citations	2 minimum	8 minimum
Peer-reviewed articles	On PI-inspired urban deliveries framework	2 minimum	Field-Weighted Citation Index (FWCI) > 1.4 per article
	presenting the green solutions uptake ABMs	1 minimum	2 publications that are core contributions to the relevant scientific fields
	presenting the project's standardisation recommendations	1 minimum	Standardisation Working Groups adopting recommendations

	presenting the results of the URBANE LLS	6 peer-reviewed articles (1 open Access)	Field-Weighted Citation Index (FWCI) > 1.4 per article
Fact Sheets	Downloads	/	50
Roadmap brochure	Downloads	/	100
Report Policy brief	Downloads	/	100
External events	Attended/presented in total	50	100
Online streaming series or webinars	Viewers	100	200
Open Innovation Days	Number of events/attendees	100	200
City platform	Members		+ 15

The effectiveness of engaging the target audience groups and the impact of the communication and dissemination activities will be monitored every **six months**, according to the success indicators and target values, set in the table above. This will allow for mitigation actions and taking specific actions toward meeting the key KPIs. Project success will be measured not only by the actions that will take place during each period, but by the incentivisation activities that will foster wider awareness raising and will engage new local communities in co-creating innovative last mile logistics solutions to meet the scale up potential of URBANE. This effort will be spearheaded by the six follower cities that will have the opportunity to use the transferability tools and develop feasibility studies, producing a valuable body knowledge from early adopters to future communities of practice. Further, URBANE will activate do-ocracy citizens' participation processes by involving 1000 citizens in user acceptance tests and enhancing the relationship between city government and society.

7. Conclusions

This plan is a **strategic roadmap for URBANE's SE/C/D/E activities**. By setting clear goals, identifying target audiences, laying out the project identity, dissemination and communication tools, stakeholder engagement activities as well as multiple outputs (events, publications, resources, etc.), this living document's main aim is to support consortium members in successfully achieving the project's goals.

The Strategy is in line with Article 17 of the Grant Agreement: “beneficiaries must promote the action and its results by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public) (...) in a strategic, coherent and effective manner.”

The URBANE engagement, dissemination and communication plan has been thorough, to link the project objectives with tangible outreach goals, including the identification of target groups, key messages to be communicated through the appropriate channels and associated networking activities. Special focus has been given to knowledge transfer actions through multiple stakeholder groups, including the Advisory Board and the Cities Platform and ongoing initiatives, aiming to serve the upscaling ambition of the project. The KPIs attainment will be monitored on a six-month basis.

8. Annex

FIGURE 5 - VISUAL OF URBANE WEBSITE

TABLE 8 – EXPLOITATION OF THE PROJECT'S MAIN RESULTS

Partners	Exploitable Results	Routes to exploitation	Potential Users & Sectors	IPR
Project and Technical Coordinator				
<i>P1-INLE</i>	Innovation Platform Transferability	Advanced Digital Twinning Platform	EU Research Consortia, Business Stakeholders, City	Open

City Stakeholders – Urban Planners Key Driver: Data-Driven Awareness and Planning for Liveable Urban Environments				
<i>P15-COBO</i> <i>P12-ITL</i>	Implementation of the NDA areas (Nearby Delivery Areas)	Sustainability of last mile delivery by deploying NDAs in Bologna, Implement SULP and update city policies Scale up in the Emilia-Romagna region	Logistics operators, City Authorities, Citizens	Open
<i>P36-KARL</i>	Parcel Robot with Tram	Fully deploy in Karlsruhe	Logistics operators, City Authorities, Citizens	Open
<i>P38-VALLAD</i>	Operational tested model with fully electric vehicles equipped with solar panels/CCAM capabilities	Fully deploy in Valladolid and knowledge/technology transfer to other administrations, municipalities, and public transport operators	Logistics operators, City Authorities, Citizens	Open
<i>P19-HELS</i> <i>P19.1FVH</i>	Hyperlocal on-demand delivery with ADVs	Fully deploy tested solution in Helsinki	Logistics operators, City Authorities, Citizens	Open
<i>P26-RCM</i>	Hub and Spoke delivery model Impact Assessment Radar	Scale up implementation in RCM region	Logistics operators, City Authorities, Citizens	Open
<i>P27-AMB</i>	Verified solution to improve operations in urban micro-hubs served by cargo-bikes.	Dissemination activities to motivate other public authorities to replicate the measure.	Logistics operators, City Authorities, Citizens	Open
<i>P34-RAV</i> <i>P35-MECH</i>	Adoption Feasibility Study	Setup LL and Implement Real Life Demonstrator	Logistics operators, City Authorities, Citizens	Open

<i>P13-AAKS</i>				
<i>P30-PRAHA</i>				
<i>P33-ANTW</i>				
<i>P31-CDA</i>				
Last mile logistics value chain operators - Key Driver: improved operations performance				
<i>P5-VAN</i>	Last mile RFID Solutions	Commercialisation of products, work with cities (AMB area) and new distribution channels	Operators, Retailers	Proprietary solution
<i>P21-DBSCH</i>	Hyperlocal on-demand delivery model	Integrate results commercial portfolio	Operators, Retailers	Proprietary Commercial IPR
<i>P24-ACS</i>	All models tested in LLS	Integrate results commercial portfolio	Operators, Retailers	Proprietary Commercial IPR
<i>P29-TYP</i>	Business model for last mile delivery	Positioning the company as sustainable	Operators, Retailers	Open
<i>P22-DTS</i>	Model for last mile delivery	Positioning the company as sustainable	Operators, Retailers	Open
Physical Innovation Providers				
<i>P23-SOBEN</i>	Commercial Exploitation	Improve existing solutions and services	Logistics operators, City Authorities	Proprietary Commercial IPR
<i>P25-LMAD</i>	Commercial Exploitation	Improve existing solutions and services	Logistics operators, City Authorities	Proprietary Commercial IPR
<i>P37-EUDRIVE</i>	Commercial Exploitation	Improve existing solutions and services	Logistics operators, City Authorities	Proprietary Commercial IPR
<i>P39-IFEVS</i>	Commercial Exploitation	Improve existing solutions and services	Logistics operators, City Authorities	Proprietary Commercial IPR

Sector Associations and Impact Strengthening Partners Key Driver: Policy Recommendations				
<i>P4-ALICE</i>	Policy Package, Adoption Roadmap, PI-urban logistics delivery model	Public-private stakeholder dialogue		Open
<i>P32-AENET</i>	Containerisation delivery - intermodal solutions combining ADVs with rail transport	Scale up in Karlsruhe		Open
<i>P3-EITUM</i>	Business models tested in LLs	<p>Help to replicate and enhance market uptake of high impact solutions across EU. Uptake LLs innovative solutions on the market to enhance sustainability of last mile delivery. Disseminate project results using its exploitation platform Marketplace of urban mobility. Tomorrow. Mobility which will have an outreach of around 25 000 professionals Our social media, which we also want to mobilise for this purpose, have an outreach of around 30k followers.</p>	Academia, Research and Business Stakeholders, Policy Makers, Standardisation Associations	Open
<i>P16-POLIS</i>	Policy Package and Adoption Roadmap	Evidence-based strategies will be disseminated and further exploited by cities across the		Open

		EU through the POLIS Network Working Groups		
Business Innovation Consultancies				
<i>P7-FIT</i>	Market Observatory for Physical Internet in Urban Logistics	National network of cities and logistics related clusters such as the Freight Leader Council (FLC), cities associations like ANCI (Associazione Nazionale Comuni Italiani), and Ministries such as the Ministry of Transport.	Logistics and local transport operators, local urban planners, research centres.	Open access
<i>P6-TRV</i>	Guidelines for customisation of Governance frameworks in collaborative city logistics	Neutral orchestration of all future city logistics ECO-system implementations.	City authorities or collaborative communities in city logistics	The multilateral community contract as an important building block of the governance framework
Research Organisations Key Driver: Integration of New Scientific Knowledge in Education and New Research				
<i>P10-KLU</i>	Physical Internet (PI)-inspired urban logistics delivery model	Integrate new knowledge in master's degree	Academia	
<i>P14-NORCE</i>	Planning and evaluating sustainable last mile logistics SEAMLESS evaluation tool	Concept development, framing of SEAMLESS tasks and outputs. Possible to further develop in order to assess other	Academia, private consultancies, public planning offices, advocacy organisations and interest groups logistics decision	NORCE researchers, academic publisher

		sustainability services	makers on all levels, business developers	
<i>P8-TUD</i>	Social simulation agent-based models (ABMs)	Assist city stakeholders in making greener decisions; Promote new knowledge in TUD Freight & Logistics Lab	Academia	Open
<i>P9-UOC</i>	RFID system and ready-to-use algorithms for cycle-logistics operating in micro-hubs	Potential replication in other cities and micro-hubs. Integrate new knowledge in master's degree in Logistics Management	Cargo owners, distributors, micro-hub operators, and fleet owners, Academia	Open
<i>P17-CERTH</i>	Impact Assessment Radar	Assist RCM in scaling up the model	Academia, City Stakeholders	Open
<i>P28-CIDAUT</i>	Innovative delivery Vehicles	Assist Valladolid in scaling up the model	Logistics operators, City Authorities	Open
<i>P20-SKEMA</i>	Business Model, Business Plans and AI algorithms	Participation in commercial ventures at city level to create the platform for pooling orders and deliveries	Commercial platform for logistic operators and city regulators	Business Model Open Algorithms IPR licensed
Innovative ICT Solution Providers- Key Driver: Exploring New Commercial Opportunities and new Services				
<i>P18-KON</i>	Smart Contracts	Include in commercial portfolio	Logistics operators, City Authorities	Commercial Technical Services
<i>P11-GEL</i>	Collaborative delivery with micro-hubs networks and light EDVs	Integrate results in GEL's commercial portfolio	Logistics operators, City Authorities	Commercial Technical Services

<i>P2-VLTN</i>	AI-driven services	Include commercial portfolio	in	Logistics operators, City Authorities	Commercial Consultancy Services
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Deliverable Scoring Sheet

URBANE Deliverable Scoring Sheet				
		Deliverable No:	D6.1	
		Deliverable Title:	Stakeholder Engagement, Dissemination and Communication Plan	
		Lead Beneficiary	Juliette Thijs (POLIS)	
		Reviewer Name	ITL	
		Review Date	[15/02/2023]	
<p><u>Grading Scheme:</u> Please paint the 'Score' box with the appropriate colour.</p>			Good quality. Perhaps some minor comments.	
			Reasonable quality, but some revision is necessary.	
			Substantial revision and / or additional work is necessary.	
<p>Please note that a red score in the 'Overall' section in the end means the deliverable must undergo peer review again to approve the revised version.</p>				
Criterion	Description	Grade	Reviewer Comments	Author Response
Language	The deliverable is easy to understand, with good use of English, and suitable terminology.			
Visuals	Fonts, figures, tables etc. are easy to read and referenced in the text.			
Glossary	The glossary of the the deliverable is complete (acronyms, unusual terms).			
Clarity	Vision, contributions & state of the art improvements are			

	discussed explicitly and are clear.			
Symbols	Mathematical symbols and nomenclature are well-defined and understood.			
Template Application	The template is successfully applied.			
References	The deliverable uses a consistent style to cite all external work referenced in the document.			
Objectives	The deliverable clearly addresses the objectives of the involved tasks.			
DoA Compliance	The content clearly contributes to the project plan and is consistent with the DoA.			
Task Mapping	It is clear which WP Tasks inform all parts of the deliverable's main content.			
Methodology	The methodological framework is explained clearly and the approach is scientifically sound.			

Contributions	Challenges are clearly addressed and the document stimulates further research.			
Conclusions	All key contributions and challenges are discussed clearly and are reflected in the deliverable.			
Overall	The deliverable is of good quality and can be finalised in time.			
Suggestions and Comments (Reviewer)				

URBANE Deliverable Scoring Sheet	
Deliverable No:	D6.1
Deliverable Title:	Stakeholder Engagement, Dissemination and Communication Plan
Lead Beneficiary	POLIS
Reviewer Name	Comune di Bologna
Review Date	[22/02/2023]
<u>Grading</u>	Good quality. Perhaps some minor comments.
<u>Scheme:</u>	Reasonable quality, but some revision is necessary.

Please paint the 'Score' box with the appropriate colour.		Substantial revision and / or additional work is necessary.		
Please note that a red score in the 'Overall' section in the end means the deliverable must undergo peer review again to approve the revised version.				
Criterion	Description	Grade	Reviewer Comments	Author Response
Language	The deliverable is easy to understand, with good use of English, and suitable terminology.		Minor revisions of text—should all be in UK spelling—not mix UK and US spelling - I revised some of these	
Visuals	Fonts, figures, tables etc. are easy to read and referenced in the text.		The font size of table/figure titles should be increased from 7 to 10 or 11—fonts of text should be uniform throughout document	
Glossary	The glossary of the deliverable is complete (acronyms, unusual terms).		I have added a few acronyms that were used in the document.	
Clarity	Vision, contributions & state of the art improvements are discussed explicitly and are clear.			
Symbols	Mathematical symbols and nomenclature are well-defined and understood.		N/A	
Template Application	The template is successfully applied.			

References	The deliverable uses a consistent style to cite all external work referenced in the document.			
Objectives	The deliverable clearly addresses the objectives of the involved tasks.			
DoA Compliance	The content clearly contributes to the project plan and is consistent with the DoA.			
Task Mapping	It is clear which WP Tasks inform all parts of the deliverable's main content.			
Methodology	The methodological framework is explained clearly and the approach is scientifically sound.			
Contributions	Challenges are clearly addressed and the document stimulates further research.			
Conclusions	All key contributions and challenges are discussed clearly and are reflected in the deliverable.			
Overall	The deliverable is of good quality and can be finalised in time.			
Suggestions and Comments (Reviewer)				

See above.

